

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PRINCIPALS' DISTRIBUTIVE JUSTICE AND TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

Ebiem, Perpetua Obianuju & Prof. Nkechi Ikediugwu
Department of Educational Management and Policy, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

Corresponding author: perpetuaju@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

This study determined the relationship between principals' distributive justice and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra state. The study adopted a correlational research design. One research question guided the study and one null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population for the study was 7027 teachers in the 266 public secondary schools in the State. The sample consisted of 1405 teachers from the six educational zones in the State. The sample was drawn using multi-stage sampling procedure which included proportionate stratified and simple random sampling techniques. Two structured questionnaires developed by the researchers titled: "Distributive Justice Questionnaire" (DJQ) and Teachers' Performance Questionnaire (TPQ) were validated by three experts and used for data collection. Cronbach's Alpha method was used to determine the internal consistency of the items in the instruments and this yielded co-efficient values of 0.75 and 0.72 for DJQ and TPQ respectively. The researcher with the aid of 12 research assistants administered a total of 1405 copies of the questionnaires on the respondents. At the end of the exercise, 1324 copies representing 94% were successfully completed, retrieved and used for data analysis. Data collected were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The result of the finding indicated that there is a very high positive relationship between principals' distributive justice and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Principals should at all times treat teachers with respect and sensitivity and explain rationale for decisions to teachers thoroughly. By doing this, principals will dismiss any wrong perceptions teachers may have regarding his decisions and this will help create positive climate that will induce improved teacher performance.

KEYWORDS

Distributive Justice, organizational justice, job performance.

Introduction

Education is of great importance to nation building. It is geared towards improving the well-being of individuals and the society at large. Education is seen as the most important instrument for preparing individuals for life and reforming the society for relevance, adequacy and competition in the world. A well administered education would equip individuals with the capacity to understand and adapt to new problems and changing situations, awaken intellectual curiosity, encourage their spirit of inquiry and make them inventive, self-reliant and resourceful.

The educational system in Nigeria has been delineated into different levels mainly pre-primary, primary, secondary and tertiary levels (Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN 2014). Secondary education which lies between the primary and tertiary level of education is considered a strategic sub-sector of the education industry because it is at this level that the youths consolidate the basic knowledge gained in primary school, and also acquire the necessary culture to become useful citizens in the society. As indicated by FRN (2014) in the National Policy on Education, the broad goals of secondary education are preparing people for useful living in the society and for higher education.

In fostering and achieving the goals of secondary education, teachers play important roles by translating the educational goals into knowledge and skill, and transferring them to students in the classroom. Teachers, as stated by Mwangi, in Obiekwe, Ogbo and Igbokwe (2020) are the pillars of the society who help students to grow and shoulder the responsibility of nation building. Teachers are indeed the nation's human capital, and every effort needs to be made to ensure they perform effectively.

The performance of teachers is one of the major factors that determine the quality of education in every education system. Teachers' job performance involves all the activities carried out by the teacher to achieve desired effects on students. It involves the extent to which the teacher participates in overall running of the school in order to achieve expected school objectives and goals. Ogundele and Olanrewaju cited in Uzoho (2021) viewed teachers' job performance as the level at which teachers in secondary schools perform their duties based on the level at which they are satisfied with their teaching job.

For optimal teachers' performance in the school, their perception of fairness and justice concerning how outcomes such as wages, promotions, work roles and workloads are distributed. Distributive Justice according to Ajala (2015) refers to outcomes being distributed proportional to inputs based on equity principle. It is the subjective evaluation of teachers to the extent to which outcomes such as wages, promotions, work roles and workloads are distributed fairly (Colquitt, Conlon, Wesson and Porter 2011, McShane and Von Glinow 2018). Distributive justice is more concerned with ensuring that there is a fair allocation of resources in the school. Fairness in allocation typically takes into cognizance the total amount of resources available for distribution, the distributing procedure and the pattern of distribution. In distributive justice the teachers' perceptions of justice in the sharing of organizational resources, expenditure, promotions, are prioritized. It also lays emphasis on issues of status, seniority, productivity, effort, needs, and the determination of payment.

Teachers who perceive fairness in the allocation of available resources by principals based on equity principle or are more likely to follow workplace rules and regulations and show extra performance and commitment towards their job and the school. In other words, teachers will repay distributive justice with hard work. Odunayo, Ayodeji, Omotolani and Oyebanji (2015) observed that when

teachers experience fair treatment from the school they are more likely to show a positive attitude, good behaviour and increased performance to the school.

The situation in secondary schools in Nigeria and indeed Anambra state shows that most principals appear to allocate tasks and positions in the school not based on merit but based on loyalty. Some have been observed to not carry their teachers along in decision making or voice their preferences when decisions are made in the school (Onyeidu, 2015). These unjust practices from principals probably are the reason most teachers display poor performance in the school, as could be observed in their poor attitude to work, absenteeism, lack of dedication to teaching and carrying out assignments, and unauthorized movement from their duty posts (Ezeugbor, 2015).

Fair processes and behaviour in the distribution of outcomes in the school arising from school principals can lead to a feeling of intellectual and emotional recognition by teachers which in turn will create trust and commitment that enhances teachers' attitude and display of performance to duties. According to Zainhpour, Fini and Minkamili in Emenike (2021) perception of injustice among teachers in school can lead them to mistrust their management, low productivity, ineffectiveness and dissatisfaction. These situations therefore made it imperative to determine the relationship between principals' distributive justice and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Principals have the responsibility of creating effective learning environment that is built and sustained by fair and just practices such as equity, tolerance, consistency, lack of bias, good representation, righteousness and flexibility. However, in Anambra state, principals seem to be highly characterized by various forms of unjust practices concerning how outcomes and resources such as wages, promotions, work roles and workloads are distributed. Personal observations by the researcher in some secondary schools in the state suggest that delegation of tasks and allocation of resources and positions in the school by principals are not based on teacher's ability or specialization but their support and loyalty to the principal. Perhaps, these series of unfair practices may be the reason most teachers display poor performance to their duties in the school, as could be observed in their poor attitude to work, absenteeism, lack of dedication to teaching and carrying out assigned tasks. These may have given rise to various disciplinary cases reported in secondary schools in Anambra State. It is as a result of the foregoing that the researcher sought answers to the question, what is the relationship between principals' distributive justice and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra state?

Research Question

1. What is the nature of relationship between principals' distributive justice and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant relationship between principals' distributive justice and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Methods

A Correlation survey research design was employed for the study. This study was carried out in the 266 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The population of the study comprised 7,027 teachers. The sample for the study is 1405 teachers drawn using multi-stage sampling procedure involving proportionate and simple random sampling techniques. This sample is representative of

20% of the population. Two researchers' developed questionnaires titled: "Distributive Justice Questionnaire" (DJQ) and Teachers' Performance Questionnaire (TPQ) were used for data collection. The instruments were subjected to face validity using three experts. A pilot test using 20 teachers from two government owned public secondary schools in Enugu State was used to ascertain the reliability of the instruments. The scores obtained from the 20 respondents were collated to determine the internal consistency of the items in each of the instruments. This was done using Cronbach's Alpha method. The reliability co-efficient for the DJQ was 0.75 while TPQ was 0.72. These scores were deemed high enough for the instrument to be taken as reliable and adequate for the study. The direct method of administration of the questionnaire was employed by the researchers. Out of the 1405 copies of the questionnaire that were distributed a total of 1324 copies were retrieved back and used for data analysis. The return rate was approximately 94% of the sample which the researcher considered satisfactory for the study. Data analysis was done using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient.

Results

Table 1: Pearson r on the Nature of Relationship between Principals' Distributive Justice and Teachers' Job Performance

Source of Variation	N	r	Remark
Distributive Justice	1324	0.88	Very High Positive Relationship
Job Performance			

Table 1 shows that there is a very high positive relationship between principals' distributive justice and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. This is evident by the size of Pearson's Correlation Coefficient r , which is 0.88.

Table 2: Test of Significance of Pearson Relationship between Principals' Distributive Justice and Teachers' Job Performance

Source of Variation	N	r	p-value	Remark
Distributive Justice	1324	0.88	0.00	Sig
Job Performance				

Analysis in Table 2 shows that there is a significant relationship between principals' distributive justice and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The calculated r (0.88) had P .value < 0.05 . The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Discussion

The finding of this study showed that there is a very high positive relationship between principals' distributive justice and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. This result implies that when outcomes such as wages, promotions, roles and workloads are distributed fairly by principal, it will lead to a very high improvement in teachers' job performance. This finding agrees with that of McKenzie and Fetter in Emenike (2021). They found that a teacher who perceives low level of justice and trust from the principal may begin to put up anti-social behaviour in the school and this will weaken her level of job performance. This finding is consistent with that of Yauvz

(2011) and Nojani (2012) that organizational justice perceptions of teachers had significant impact on their performance and commitment.

The finding of this study also aligns with that of Becerra, (2010); Othman and Wanlabelh, (2012) and Vogel, (2012). These researchers found that a leader that is sincere and fair in allocation of school's resources will encourage teachers to feel more committed towards performing their job. A failure of leadership in providing fair distribution of resources will cause teachers to fail in the performance to their work.

The finding of the corresponding hypothesis shows that there is a significant relationship between principals' distributive justice and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding supports that of Rouzbahani, Soleimani, Rezai and Hemati (2013) who found a strong positive and significant relationship between fairness in leadership and organizational performance.

Conclusion

From the findings of this study the researchers concluded there is a very high positive relationship between principals' distributive justice and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. This result implies that when school's resources and outcomes such as wages, promotions, roles and workloads are distributed fairly by principal, it will lead to a very high improvement in teachers' job performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Secondary school principals should constantly display fairness in the distribution and allocation of resources and positions, roles and workloads in the school in order to stimulate teachers' improved performance.
2. Principals should at all times treat teachers with respect and sensitivity and explain rationale for decisions to teachers thoroughly. By doing this, principals will dismiss any wrong perceptions teachers may have regarding his decisions and this will help create positive climate that will induce improved teacher performance.

References

- Ajala, E.M. (2015). The influence of organisational justice on employees' commitment in manufacturing firms in Oyo State, Nigeria: implications for industrial social work. *African Journal of Social Work*, 5(1), 92-130.
- Becerra, C.C. (2010). Ethical practice: a study of Chilean school leader. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 50 (4) 420-436.
- Colquitt, J., Conlon, D., Wesson, M., Porter, C., and Ng, K. (2021). Justice at the Millennium: A Meta-analytic Review of 25 Years of Organizational Justice Research. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86, 425-445.
- Colquitt, J.A, Colon, T, Wesson, D.T and Porter, L. (2011). Justice, trust and trustworthiness: a longitudinal analysis integrating three theoretical perspectives. *Academy of Management Journal*, 3(4), 188-206. Retrieved from <http://www.press.brkp/cp/v42n/en-16.pdf>.
- Emenike, C.B., and Nwogbo, V.N. (2021). Teachers' perception of organizational justice as a correlate of their job commitment in secondary schools in Anambra State. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 3(1), 89-100.
- Ezeugbor, C.O. (2015), Influence of principals' ethical leadership behaviours on teachers' level of commitment in secondary schools in Anambra state, Nigeria. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 3(9), 513-526.
- FRN (2014). *National Policy on Education*. (6th edition) Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Mcshane, S. and Glinow, M.V. (2018). *Organizational behaviour: Emerging knowledge, global reality (8th Ed.)*, America: McGraw-Hill Irwin.
- Nojani, M.; Arjmandnia, A.; Afrooz, G. and Rajabi, M. (2012) The Study on Relationship Between Organizational Justice and Job Satisfaction in Teachers Working in General, Special and Gifted Education Systems, *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 46, 2900-2905.
- Obiekwe, K.K., Ogbo, R.N., and Igbokwe, I.C. (2020). Relationship between principals' communicative and decisional ethical leadership behaviour and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 8(6), 1748-1756.
- Odunayo. A., Ayodeji. A., Omotolani. O. and Oyebanji. O. (2015). Influence of perceived organizational justice on teachers' commitment in selected secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Journal of Scientific Research and Reports* 4(7), 605-613.
- Onyeidu (2015). The impact of organizational justice on employees' job satisfaction and job commitment in south east, Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Research*. 7, (3)38-49.
- Othman, A. and Wanlabeh, N. (2012). Teachers' perspectives on leadership practices and motivation in Islamic private schools, Southern Thailand, *Asian Education and Development Studies*, 1(3), 237-250.

- Rouzbahani, M.A., Soleimanian, Z., Rezai, F.B and Hemati, A. (2013). The Relationship between Ethical Leadership with the Three Dimensions of Organizational Commitment (Affective, Continuous, Normative) and Confidence in Superintendent. *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*, 3, (6) 771-776.
- Uzoho, I. (2021). Teachers' perception of principals' adversity quotient as correlate of their job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. *Unpublished Masters' Thesis, Department of Educational Management and Policy, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.*
- Vogel, L., R, (2012). Leading with hearts and minds: ethical orientations of educational leadership doctoral students. *Values and Ethics in Educational Administration*, 10(1), 1-12.
- Yavuz, M. (2011). The effects of teachers' perception of organizational justice and culture on organizational commitment. *African Journal of Business Management*, 4(5), 695-701.